

Mixed Cellular Hodgkin Lymphoma in the Parotid Gland, Case Report.

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ABSTRACT

Lymphoma is a group of pathologies with diverse clinical and histological characteristics. Hodgkin lymphomas typically occur in extranodal sites in 1%. Parotid gland lymphomas constitute only 0.2–0.8% of all malignant tumors of this gland. There is currently no consensus on diagnosis and treatment, and published data are scarce and heterogeneous.

We present the case of a 68-year-old male patient with no significant medical history who presented with a mass in the left submandibular region that had been present for one month. Ultrasound was performed as a diagnostic approach, ultimately deciding on an excisional biopsy. The histopathological report revealed mixed cellular Hodgkin lymphoma in the parotid gland. This case was observed at Rural Hospital of VillaunióN No. 16, Mexican Social Security Institute (IMSS), VillaunióN, Sinaloa, México, during the specialty's outreach service.

KEYWORDS: Lymphoma, Hodgkin, lymphoid tissue, parotid gland, lymph nodes.

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INTRODUCTION

Lymphoma is a group of pathologies with distinct clinical and histological characteristics, genetic abnormalities, and immunophenotypes. This group affects lymphoid tissue. They can be classified into two main subtypes: Hodgkin lymphoma and non-Hodgkin lymphoma. The first group can be derived from T, B, and NK cells, and is mostly located extranodally in the digestive tract, salivary glands, jaw, etc.; while the other group generally presents as lymph node-mediated disease. Non-Hodgkin lymphomas are more prevalent than Hodgkin lymphomas (1, 2).

The primary involvement of these lymphomas is the lymph nodes; however, 25% of NHL and 1% of HL originate in extranodal sites such as the gastrointestinal tract, head and neck, CNS, etc. (2).

Parotid gland lymphomas constitute only 0.2–0.8% of all malignant tumors of this gland. There is currently no consensus on diagnosis and treatment, and published data are scarce and heterogeneous. Of this percentage, and as mentioned, the most common lymphomas are extranodal NHLs. Therefore, Hodgkin lymphoma is exceptionally rare, representing only 4% of all parotid lymphomas. Its peak incidence is usually between 50 and 80 years of age, with an

average age of 55 to 65 years, and an even gender distribution (2, 3).

Diagnosis is complex since the clinical picture and imaging studies fail to establish a differential diagnosis from other types of parotid gland tumors. Therefore, a series of minimally invasive procedures, such as needle biopsies or surgical removal, are required to establish a histopathological diagnosis (4).

The clinical picture is nonspecific and unclear. Patients are asymptomatic in the early stages. However, when patients develop facial symptoms, the most common symptom is the identification of a mass, which presents with progressive and rapid growth, changes in skin texture, and, in some cases, facial nerve involvement, such as facial pain and paralysis. These symptoms are associated with a high suspicion of malignancy. In other cases, the patient presents with B symptoms; however, this presentation is rare (2, 5, 6).

Definitive diagnosis is based on histopathological examination, immunohistochemistry, and genetic testing of the tissue sample to identify the lymphoma subtype and establish treatment options (2).

Being an infrequent pathology, it is difficult to conclude the clinical presentation, associated risk factors, management and

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prognosis due to the scarcity of literature and lack of information, even most of the literature consists of case reports that provide unique findings without documenting risk factors, detailed treatment and long-term results necessary to predict the prognosis and establish a consensus for its management (6, 7).

Treatment is not well established; there are no current lines of treatment. However, in general, Hodgkin lymphomas are chemo- and radiosensitive and generally respond well. In other cases, surgical resection is performed initially, followed by complementary chemotherapy, or surgical treatment alone is chosen with close follow-up and complementary imaging studies to prevent residual disease or recurrence. This has not been studied in depth, hence the importance of establishing a formal treatment (8, 9).

Surgical treatment also varies. Some reports have resorted to total parotidectomy with or without facial nerve preservation, partial parotidectomy, or only excisional biopsy with negative margins with adjuvant chemoradiation, given the propensity for recurrence. Some reports establish treatment based on the degree of differentiation: low-grade lymphoma can be treated with radiotherapy alone, while diffuse high-grade lymphoma is treated with aggressive chemotherapy, combining radiotherapy and chemotherapy as appropriate (1, 2, 10).

This study presents a case of mixed cellularity classical Hodgkin lymphoma of the parotid gland.

CASE DESCRIPTION

A 68-year-old male patient denies any chronic illnesses, is allergic to penicillin, and has a surgical history of amputation of the second finger of his right hand due to a work-related accident. He presented to a primary care clinic, reporting a mass in the left submandibular region that had progressively increased in size one month earlier. He denied pain, fever, weight loss, or any other clinical findings.

A guided physical examination revealed a cylindrical neck, with a left cervical mass at level 1B, in the submandibular region, extending to the parotid gland. It was approximately 4 x 4 cm in size, indurated, mobile, not fixed to deep planes, and painless on palpation. A neck ultrasound was requested, reporting a superficial cystic nodule with thin walls, fine ovoid edges and peripheral vascularity, measuring 35 x 22 x 25 mm, located in the posterolateral edge of the parotid gland. Adjacent to the superficial parotid gland, a hypoechoic mass with regular edges measuring 10 x 12 mm was observed. It was concluded as a predominantly cystic nodule in the left submandibular region with a mass apparently dependent on the parotid gland.

The patient was referred to the General Surgery Department and scheduled for excisional biopsy versus superficial parotidectomy with facial nerve preservation.

During surgery, the patient was placed supine, with cervical lateralization on the right side and neck hyperextension. Using the Rosier technique, a modified Blair incision was made, extending from the preauricular region to the neck in

an "S" shape. The incision was dissected in layers, first creating the skin flaps until the parotid gland was observed. A solid mass was palpated in the superficial parotid gland toward the lower portion, extending with a cervical lymph node in the submandibular region (Figures 1).

FIGURE 1. Cervical adenopathy measuring 4x4 cm in the left submandibular area, adhered to vessels, superficial parotid gland with a 1x1 cm mass.

It was decided to perform a total excision of the adjacent lymph node, after exposing the anterior border of the sternocleidomastoid muscle and the posterior belly of the digastric muscle. The external jugular vein was lateralized, the facial nerve trunk was located with blunt dissection to preserve it, and the lymph node was separated from the parotid gland. Hemostasis was verified, and the procedure was completed (Figure 2).

FIGURE 2. Total excision of adenopathy.

The patient was kept under observation for 24 hours, with good postoperative progress, without clinical involvement of the facial nerve.

He returned to the clinic one month later for follow-up, with a histopathology report indicating mixed cellular Hodgkin lymphoma, pending immunohistochemistry (Figure 3).

Mixed Cellular Hodgkin Lymphoma in the Parotid Gland, Case Report.

FIGURE 3. Microscopic image with lymphoid tissue characterized by loss of architecture and consisting of proliferation of cells with aberrant nuclei of dispersed chromatin and prominent nucleoli (Hodgkin cells), alternating with plasma cells, lymphocytes and eosinophils.

He was referred to a third-level hospital to Internal Medicine and Hematology, who completed the protocol, blood tests were requested with values within normal parameters, viral panel for Epstein-Barr virus, cytomegalovirus, herpes and human immunodeficiency virus, with detection of negative serologies, extension studies with computed tomography detecting a superficial parotid mass of 10 x 11 mm, without detecting any other lesion. Immunohistochemistry revealed positive markers for CD15, CD30 and PAX-5. Confirming the diagnosis of primary mixed cellular Hodgkin lymphoma in the parotid gland, granting a TNM of T2, N0, M0, in clinical stage II, granting medical treatment based on chemotherapy and radiotherapy until complete remission.

DISCUSSION

Hodgkin lymphoma is a lymphoid neoplasm that represents approximately 10% of all lymphomas and presents with a classic bimodal presentation. Its initial peak is in young adults and its second peak is in adults over 55 years of age (1, 2). This clinical case describes a 68-year-old patient who presented with persistent submandibular adenopathy. Histopathologically, the diagnosis was classical Hodgkin lymphoma, mixed cellularity subtype. This variant represents approximately 15–25% of HL cases and is more frequently observed in older men, which matches the profile of our patient (2, 3).

The location of the submandibular adenopathy is uncommon, as the cervical and supraclavicular lymph nodes are usually the most affected in Hodgkin lymphoma. Differential diagnoses should be made with inflammatory, metastatic, and infectious processes (4).

Mixed cellular Hodgkin lymphoma is usually associated with advanced disease at the time of diagnosis (stages III-IV) and B symptoms (fever, weight loss, and nocturnal sweating), although in this case the patient did not report systemic symptoms. The presentation without systemic symptoms and with localized adenopathy could represent an early-stage diagnosis, which has positive implications for the patient's prognosis (2, 5, 6).

Histologically, the mixed cellularity subtype is characterized by abundant inflammatory infiltrate and classic Reed-Sternberg cells. An immunohistochemical study should be performed to make a confirmatory diagnosis. The CD30+ and CD15+ immunohistochemical profile would support the diagnosis of classic HL (6, 7).

Regarding treatment, patients over 60 years of age pose a challenge due to the presence of comorbidities and lower tolerance to chemotherapy regimens. In these cases, a comprehensive geriatric assessment and a multidisciplinary approach are essential for patient treatment (8, 9).

We must maintain a high level of diagnostic suspicion in older patients with atypical lymphadenopathy, even if they have not presented constitutional symptoms. It is important to adapt therapeutic strategies in this type of patient based on their age and clinical condition to maximize treatment efficacy (9, 10).

CONCLUSION

Hodgkin lymphoma of the parotid gland is a rare case; however, there are isolated case reports that make us reflect on its presentation and diagnostic suspicion. Therefore, a comprehensive diagnosis supported by various services can improve the diagnostic and therapeutic pathway, leading to a better prognosis for patients.

Although there is no standardized diagnostic pathway, clinical suspicion, supported by ultrasound as an initial study, and laboratory testing guide us in deciding whether to perform an excisional biopsy to obtain a histopathological result as a definitive diagnosis and to be able to refer for timely treatment.

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Mixed Cellular Hodgkin Lymphoma in the Parotid Gland, Case Report.

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